

A FEDERATED LEARNING BASE ANOMALY DETECTION SOLUTION

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Abstract.

Adhering to NIST guidelines and the NIS Directive is essential for securing Internet of Things (IoT) ecosystems, which face growing cybersecurity and privacy risks due to their expanding attack surface. Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) are critical for monitoring network traffic and identifying threats. While traditional IDS rely on signature-based detection, modern systems must also incorporate anomaly detection to identify unknown threats and zero-day attacks by analysing deviations from normal behaviour.

However, deploying anomaly detection in resource-constrained IoT environments poses challenges, including increased computational load and risks associated with centralized data analysis. To address these concerns, this paper investigates the application of **federated learning (FL)** as a privacy-preserving approach to anomaly detection in IoT networks. FL allows decentralized model training across devices without sharing raw data, enhancing both privacy and scalability. This paper highlights the benefits and trade-offs of FL-based IDS, emphasizing the need for solutions that balance detection accuracy, system performance, and data privacy in securing future IoT infrastructures.

In the realm of cybersecurity and data privacy, Internet of Things (IoT) devices introduce significant vulnerabilities due to their extensive deployment and integration across interconnected systems. These devices often communicate both internally with other system components and externally with remote services, creating multiple points of entry for potential cyber threats. If not equipped with robust security protocols, IoT devices can become gateways for attackers, jeopardizing the integrity of the entire network and increasing the risk of data breaches that can severely undermine user privacy.

Mitigating these threats requires a comprehensive approach to securing the underlying infrastructure against both unauthorized access and malicious behaviours. As cyberattacks evolve in complexity and frequency, research into intrusion detection has increasingly focused on anomaly detection techniques. These methods attempt to identify suspicious or previously unseen activities by examining patterns and deviations from historical behavioural data.

However, the implementation of anomaly detection in IoT ecosystems presents its own challenges. These systems often operate with limited processing power and resources, and introducing complex detection algorithms can degrade system

performance or even compromise user privacy if not carefully managed. Additionally, centralized models that aggregate traffic data for analysis may offer enhanced detection capabilities due to access to larger datasets, but they also elevate the risk of privacy breaches. If such data is not thoroughly anonymized and secured, it could inadvertently expose sensitive information.

In these circumstances, Federated Learning with its decentralized approach can help in identifying anomalous behaviour, in fact it has becoming an emerging topic in recent research [1][2].

With these assumptions we build an *Anomaly-Based Component for Intrusion Detection* that aims at identifying anomalies while applying Federated Learning Approach [3][4], more precisely is to “Collaboratively identifying deviations from normal patterns, potential ability to detect distributed threats or emerging vulnerabilities while preserving data privacy across the network”.

The main reasons which are also the benefit provide by the approach are:

- decentralized training - detection model is collaboratively generated by peer devices to distribute effort;
- every device can update the detection model locally for specific local conditions and/or traffic patterns;
- privacy is preserved because peer detection models are aggregated by the centralized node but without sharing peer dataset;
- the detection is applied at device level, potentially identifying distributed anomalous events.

The steps for FL training are:

1. model0 initialization in central node (or FL server)
2. Sending model0 to device in the federation
3. Local detection model training using local dataset
4. Returning model parameters to the central node
5. Aggregation of the model parameters into a new detection model modelz
6. Repeat steps 1 to 5 until the model converges

The aggregated model is saved as global model, sent to all devices in the federation for local anomaly detection. During operational phase the model is used to analyse the network traffic in real-time on the device/participant and identifying what is normal to what is anormal.

Two important aspects to consider for Federated Learning approach that can potentially alter results are:

- the aggregation algorithm used by the server to aggregate model updates;
- the algorithm used by the client to train the anomaly detection model.

The key is to select the best combination of the two for the type of anomaly detection to be applied and the context: fine tuning is important stage of designing machine learning (ML) based solutions.

Figure 1 - Federated Learning, collaborative detection model training

Federated Learning optimisation is a hot topic and research are still ongoing to identify optimized methods for model convergence [5].

In the following table, a list of potential aggregation strategies and algorithms that are potentially used.

Table 1 - Federated Learning potential aggregation algorithms

Name	Description	Benefits
Federated Averaging (FedAVG)	The server performs weighted average of model updates from different clients when data is mostly homogenous	Simple, intuitive, easy to implement
Federated Proximal (FedProx)	It is based on FedAVG but introduce a limit (proximal term) in how much local models can deviate from the global model	Useful when data is heterogenous
Federated Optimisation (FedOpt)	Is a family of optimisation algorithms that introduces adaptive optimizers	Useful when data is heterogenous and potentially improves coverage speed

On the algorithm used by the FL participants or clients, there are three potential categories that define the type of anomaly detection being performed:

- Deep Learning-Based Anomaly Detection – uses deep learning models to detect complex high-dimensional anomalies;
- Machine Learning-Based Approaches - uses supervised or unsupervised ML models to classify normal vs. anomalous instances;
- Statistical Approaches – uses statistical methods for their lightweight and interpretability

Data distribution of the dataset used for training is also a relevant factor that can impact the accuracy, robustness and effectiveness of the detection system, - Independent and Identically Distributed (IID) or non-IID, others are the client Participation and dropout Rate, the synchronization, etc. but this first Proof of Concept (PoC) focus on few of them.

To start the process, data processing is an essential step to convey to a specific and predefined structure of the data: the standard used is the Netflow¹, suitable for its standardized and detailed capture of traffic flow data; it includes critical information such as IP addresses, port numbers, and byte and packet counts, which are essential for detecting anomalous behaviour in network traffic.

For this POC we used Flower FedMedian as aggregation strategy, which is based on FedAVG and we used Logistic Regression for Training and inference on the participant. The dataset used for training is the NF-ToN-IoT² provided by the Cyber Security Research Group at the University of New South Wales (UNSW), Australia, led by Dr. Nour Moustafa. Anomaly detection methods typically operate under the assumption that benign (normal) traffic significantly outweighs malicious activity, allowing anomalies to stand out clearly. However, the NF-ToN-IoT dataset used in this study is highly imbalanced, with a disproportionately large number of malicious packets compared to benign ones. This imbalance risks skewing the model's learning process, potentially leading it to misclassify malicious behaviour as normal, resulting in a high false positive rate. To mitigate this issue a subset of the NF-ToN-IoT dataset (approximately 90,000 records, or 6.5% of the full set) was combined with 10,000 synthetically generated benign records to create a more balanced dataset. This combined dataset was then split into 80% for training and 20% for testing, using 12 selected features.

After 30 rounds of federated aggregation, the model achieved an accuracy of 96%, see *Figure 2*: the model quickly improved its accuracy in the early training rounds and gradually slowed down, eventually reaching a stable accuracy close to

¹ NetFlow is a network protocol created by Cisco that collects IP traffic information, making it a standard for traffic analytics in network management

² <https://research.unsw.edu.au/projects/toniot-datasets>

96%, which means it increases very quickly at first, then slows down over time, approaching a maximum value.. This behaviour is typical of exponential learning curves, the accuracy $A(r)$ is approximated by:

$$A(r) = 0.96 - 0.41 * e^{-0.10r}$$

This reflects a stable, generalizing model using FedAVG with Logistic regression. However, these results should be interpreted with caution. The synthetic benign data may not accurately reflect real-world traffic patterns, potentially introducing bias and giving a misleading impression of the model's performance. As a result, the model may perform well under test conditions but fail to generalize effectively in real deployment scenarios.

Further analysis will continue focusing on data preprocessing, dataset distribution, accuracy over combination of aggregation algorithm and the participant algorithm.

Figure 2 - Accuracy calculated in 30 rounds

Literature

1. Rey, V., Sánchez, P. M., Celdrán, A. H., & Bovet, G. (2022). Federated learning for malware detection in IoT devices. *Computer Networks*, 204.
2. Nguyen, T. D., Marchal, S., Miettinen, M., Fereidooni, H., Asokan, N., & Sadeghi, A. -R. (2019). D²IoT: A Federated Self-learning Anomaly Detection System for IoT. 2019 IEEE 39th International Conference on Distributed Computing Systems (ICDCS). Dallas, TX, USA.

3. Brendan McMahan, H., Moore, E., Ramage, D., Hampson, S., & Aguera y Arcas, B. (2017). Communication-Efficient Learning of Deep Networks from Decentralized Data. *20th International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Statistics, AISTATS 2017*.
4. Yang, Q., Liu, Y., Chen, T., & Tong, Y. (2019). Federated machine learning: Concept and applications. *ACM Transactions on Intelligent Systems and Technologies (TIST)*, 10(2).
5. Reddi, S., Charles, Z. B., Zaheer, M., Garrett, Z., Rush, K., Konečný, J., . . . Brendan McMahan, H. (2021). Adaptive Federated Optimization. *International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR 2021)*.